

FutureEUAqua – FUTURE GROWTH IN SUSTAINABLE, RESILIENT AND CLIMATE FRIENDLY ORGANIC AND CONVENTIONAL EUROPEAN AQUACULTURE

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Content

European aquaculture production has reached 1.25 million tonnes of seafood annually, with a value of over 4 billion euro. Of this amount, 4% is certified as organic, amounting in 2015 to a total of approximately 50,000 tonnes (EUMOFA, 2017). In 2015, EU consumers spent 54 billion euro for buying fisheries and aquaculture products, reaching the highest amount ever recorded (EUMOFA, 2017). Nevertheless, Europe is still heavily dependent on external markets to cover this demand. The increased demand for aquaculture products has to be covered at the same time as food production need to be more sustainable, climate friendly and supporting the UN Sustainable goals.

The newly started EU project FutureEUAqua aims to effectively promote sustainable growth in aquaculture that is resilient to climate changes, and environmental friendly organic and conventional aquaculture of major fish species in Europe. It is a well-documented assumption that aquaculture that will meet future challenges with respect to the growing consumer demand for high quality, nutritious and responsibly produced food. FutureEUAqua will promote innovations in the whole value chain, including genetic selection, ingredients and feeds, non-invasive monitoring technologies, innovative fish products and packaging methods, optimal production systems such as IMTA and RAS, taking into account socioeconomic considerations by the participation of a wide spectrum of stakeholders, training and dissemination activities.

To achieve these ambiguous goals, 32 partners from R&D, industry and associations, originating from nine countries will collaborate in research, training, dissemination and contact with stakeholders through e.g. stakeholder events.

FutureEUAqua will contribute with innovations that will arrive Technology readiness level (TRL) ranging from five to nine. Innovations will result from all research topics, including sustainable genotypes, feeds and farming management solutions; smart tools to monitor the farming environment that guarantee aquatic animal health and welfare, tailor-made aquaculture fresh/processed foods and packaging, IT tools and information packages to improve consumer's awareness about aquaculture products and related markets.

Figure 1. Structure of FutureEUAqua

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The results and innovations will have impacts by improving resilience and sustainability of aquaculture farming systems and practices. The results will have impact on a diversity of end users representing the whole value chain from breeding companies to processing plants and intelligent packaging, including e.g. digital farming solutions for improved animal health and welfare, retailers and customer care providers. We intend to gather stakeholders to contribute to the professional skills and competences of those working and being trained to work within the blue economy and support the implementation of the EU Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) and contribute to policymaking in research, innovation and technology.

The outcomes and recommendations will be presented at the two planned stakeholder events, and discussed at the dedicated conference at the end of the project's timeline. These meetings will address all stakeholders and interest groups affected by the scope of FutureEUAqua. A final roadmap for the exploitation of results, including efforts for technology transfer will be presented at the final conference.

References

EUMOFA (2017). EU Organic Aquaculture; www.eumofa.eu, http://www.eumofa.eu/documents/20178/84590/Study+report_organic+aquaculture.pdf

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